

Rhodanines. Part I. Synthesis of 3-Aryl/benzyl-5-alkyl/aryl-rhodanines

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Aryl/benzylammonium dithiocarbamates have been condensed with α -halo-fatty acids and α -halo-arylacetic acids to yield the title compounds.

Bradsher *et al.*¹ have synthesised rhodanines with aryl/benzyl groups at 3-position and found them to exhibit fungitoxic and bacteriostatic activity. Very few rhodanines with a substituent at 5-position have been studied. Bashour² has found 3-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-5-methyl/ethylrhodanines to possess insecticidal, fungicidal, and nematocidal properties. In order to study their physiological activity, it was thought desirable to prepare rhodanines with alkyl/aryl groups at 5-position and aryl/benzyl groups at 3-position. With this end in view, α -halo-fatty acids and α -halo-arylacetic acids (as sodium salts) have been condensed with aryl/benzylammonium dithiocarbamates (not isolated) from the corresponding amines to yield 3-aryl/benzyl-5-alkyl/aryl-rhodanines.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Halo-arylacetic acids were prepared as described by Raval and Trivedi³. Condensation of different dithiocarbamates (not isolated) with α -halo-fatty acids and α -halo-arylacetic acids was carried out as described by Bradsher *et al.*¹. Rhodanines (yields about 50%) were crystallised from ethanol. Compounds are listed in Tables I and II.

3-Aryl-5-alkyl/aryl-rhodanines.

X.	M.P.	Formula. R=Me.	%Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
H	117°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ONS ₂	28.5	28.7
<i>o</i> -Cl	152°	C ₁₀ H ₈ ONClS ₂	24.7	24.9
<i>m</i> -Cl	106°	"	25.1	"
<i>o</i> -Me	180°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ONS ₂	26.9	27.0
<i>m</i> -Me	124°	"	27.1	"
<i>p</i> -Me	196°	"	26.8	"
<i>o</i> -OMe	137°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS ₂	25.1	25.3
<i>p</i> -OMe	178°	"	25.4	"
<i>p</i> -Br	145°	C ₁₀ H ₈ ONBrS ₂	21.0	21.2
2,5-DiCl	132°	C ₁₀ H ₇ ONCl ₂ S ₂	22.0	21.9

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1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 384.
2. U. S. P. 2743211/1956; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, **50**, 11595.
3. *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 733.

TABLE I (contd.)

X.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.
R = Et.				
H	85°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ONS ₂	28.8	27.0
<i>o</i> -Cl	152°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONClS ₂	23.5	23.6
<i>m</i> -Cl	110°	"	23.8	"
<i>o</i> -Me	102°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONS ₂	25.3	25.5
<i>m</i> -Me	113°	"	25.7	"
<i>p</i> -Me	93°	"	25.6	"
<i>p</i> -Br	92°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ONBrS ₂	20.5	20.3
2,5-DiCl	134°	C ₁₁ H ₉ ONCl ₂ S ₂	21.1	20.9
<i>o</i> -OMe	125°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ NS ₂	24.2	24.0
<i>p</i> -OMe	93°	"	23.8	"
R = Bun.				
H	88°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ONS ₂	24.0	24.2
<i>p</i> -Cl	106°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ ONClS ₂	21.5	21.4
<i>o</i> -Me	170°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONS ₂	23.0	22.9
<i>p</i> -Me	97°	"	23.1	22.9
<i>o</i> -OMe	91°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS ₂	21.8	21.7
<i>p</i> -OMe	92°	"	21.5	"
<i>p</i> -Br	104°	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ ONBrS ₂	18.8	18.6
R = Ph.				
H	150°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ONS ₂	22.7	22.5
<i>o</i> -Cl	151°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ONClS ₂	19.8	20.0
<i>m</i> -Cl	220°	"	10.9	"
<i>p</i> -Cl	138°	"	20.2	"
<i>o</i> -Me	169°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ONS ₂	21.2	21.4
<i>p</i> -Me	179°	"	21.3	"
<i>p</i> -OMe	132°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS ₂	20.2	20.3
R = <i>o</i> -ClPh.				
H	160°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ONClS ₂	19.0	20.0
<i>o</i> -Cl	110°	C ₁₅ H ₉ ONCl ₂ S ₂	18.0	18.1
<i>m</i> -Cl	122°	"	18.2	"
<i>p</i> -Cl	180°	"	18.3	"
<i>o</i> -Me	186°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ONClS ₂	19.0	19.2
<i>p</i> -Me	118°	"	19.4	"

TABLE II

3-Benzyl-5-alkyl|aryl-rhodanines.

R.	X.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
Me	H	145°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ONS ₂	28.9	27.0
Et	H	85°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ONS ₂	25.3	25.5
Pr ⁿ	H	140°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ONS ₂	24.0	24.2
Bun ⁿ	H	189°	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ ONS ₂	23.0	22.9
"	<i>o</i> -Cl	142°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ONClS ₂	22.0	22.2
Ph	H	234°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ONS ₂	21.6	21.4
"	<i>m</i> -Me	140°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ONS ₂	20.7	20.5
<i>o</i> -ClPh	H	112°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ONClS ₂	19.0	19.2

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